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Education and community in India: What do expect from each other?

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Abstract:

In this backdrop, community and students often consider a routine teaching-learning in school/ higher educational institution as inadequate. They demand much more what the system of higher education is delivering. Thus, the students and their community explore an additional assistance to compete with their peers and to achieve the best. The objective of the study is to understand the present isolation between the school and the community through social service and collaboration with various agencies of the community. A regress investigation is done through different literature and field notes of the researcher. Conclusion:

Community should aim at providing 'Education for All' by meeting the expenditure as far as possible. Mobilise individual support for compulsory elementary education for children in the age group of 6-14. There is a gap between expectation of the community and outcome of the present system of education.

Keyword: Adult learner, education, community, RTE, Higher education

Introduction:

In this era of cut-throat competition and scarcity of opportunities (either for admission in so called premier higher education institution or getting a desired employment), one has to have the best academic achievement and skills to grab the opportunity. The gravity of the competition can be understood with government job applicants. 'Civil Services Examination' (CSE) is considered to be the toughest exam for the highest administrative powers and responsibility. It is the most prestigious examination for recruitment in government services in India, for instance, in the year 2018 (final result declared in April, 2019), approximately three hundred thousand aspirants applied against 812 vacancies for CSE (Government of India, 2019). Thus, there were 369 aspirants per vacancy for CSE for the year 2018. This is just one out of It is just the tip of the iceberg. A ruthless competition can be noticed not only for government services but also for admission in academic, technical, and professional courses offered by reputed institutions. Competition is one of the reasons that propel private tuition. The competition leads to a system of learning which aims to qualify a particular examination. According to Percy (2004) "private tutoring is, to a large extent, a by-product of examination-oriented learning or examination-driven school curricula" (p.1).

In this backdrop, community and students often consider a routine teaching-learning in school/ higher educational institution as inadequate. They demand much more what the system of higher education is delivering. Thus, the students and their community explore an additional assistance to compete with their peers and to achieve the best. This competition and drive to achieve the best is inculcated culturally and socially especially in India. According to Sujatha (2014) "a culture of comparing and competing with the peer

group, relatives and kin group, and the social obsession with education, are common social features of middle-class Indian society”.

Often, community and students consider high academic achievement as a guarantee for successful career. Therefore, community select a ‘good school’ as a first step within their access and affordability or even sometimes beyond their economic affordability. Even though, community are still not assured about the high academic achievement of their children in this competitive era. Secondly, to doubly assure high academic achievement of the children and prepare them for this ruthless competitive era, community arrange additional help in terms of private tuition for their wards.

Meaning of Community

Allen and Cook look at the community as the 'population aggregate inhabiting a delimitable contiguous territory, sharing a historical heritage, possessing a set of basic service institutions. participating in a common mode of life, and being conscious of its unity to enable it to act in a corporate way.

G.D.H. Cole. "By a community I mean a complex of social life, a complex including a number of human beings, living together under conditions of social relationships, bound together by a common, however constantly changing, stock of conventions, customs and traditions and conscious to some extent of common social objects and interests."

Difference Between "Society" and "Community"

Ottawa's Concept of Society and Community: "Society" and "Community" are usually used as synonymous terms. But there is a very fine difference between the two organizations where people live together. It refers to a definite group of people living in a geographical territory and being conscious of their lifestyles and aims of life. A community also means a group of people living in a geographical territory. But they are not conscious of their lifestyles and purpose of life. That is why children constitute the community, not the society. Unless they are conscious of the way their society functions and of their rights and duties as its full citizens, they cannot be taken as members of the society.

According to Ottawa (1962). "A community is everybody, adults and children, social and non-social persons, living in a certain territory or purpose. A society is a kind of community (or a part of a community) whose members have become socially conscious of their mode of life and are united by a common set of aims and values".

ii) Society is more conscious and organised: A society is therefore a part of the community. It is well organised and specific, whereas a community is not properly integrated and it is general or broad. A community or society is never static. Both are dynamic, always changing. But in a society its members are more conscious of their values, needs, hopes and aspirations. The members of the society are socially more conscious and emotionally more organised than those of a community.

Both the society and community possess some common characteristics: These are characterized by a group of people, a geographical territory and a spirit of belongingness.

Nature of Community

Thus, a community is a social group living in a particular area and sharing a common cultural heritage.

Its members are driven by "community belongingness" and community sentiment.

◆ The members are governed by common needs, purposes, objectives and ideals.

The members of the community celebrate common festivals, cultural items, and literal activities to strengthen the bond of universal brotherhood.

The members will sacrifice 'self' before 'common cause' and work for the common cause.

◆ Ideals, vision and progressive thoughts of individual members will influence the community and change their outlook.

The concept that they are members of the community will develop 'security' among the members.

Objectives of Community Education

To understand the community.

To develop sensitivity of students towards the needs, problems and aspirations of the community. To develop communicative and social skills of students.

To develop specific traits in students like adaptability. involvement, leadership and cooperation.

The break isolation between the school and the community through social service and collaboration with various agencies of the community.

Components of Community Education

Study of community functions.

Organisations of parent-teacher meetings.

Establishment of youth clubs.

Organising community surveys.

Interviewing community leaders, professional workgroups. Establishing links with community services like hospitals, transportation agencies, telephone exchanges, post offices, etc. Study of communities' tension areas of social prejudices, discrimination and backwardness.

Study of local needs and problems.

The curricular use of community resources both human and material.

Inviting professionals from the community for special talks in schools can be very educative for students. Also, outings, vis and field trips to community resources can be helpful.

Community in Different Socio-Economic and Cultural Contexts.

School in the Socio-economic Context. School as A miniature Society

a) John Dewey's Concept of the School: The distinguished educationist John Dewey desired "to make each one of our schools as embryonic community life, active with types of occupations that reflect the life of the larger society and permeated throughout with the spirit of art, history and science. When the school introduces and trains each child of society, into membership within such a little community, saturating him with the spirit of service and providing him with instrument of effective self-direction, we shall have the deepest and best guarantees of a large society which is worthy, lovely and harmonious."

According to Dewey, the school is a miniature society. It is a social institution to serve its purposes. It has to train and bring up the students in such a way that the students will be able to participate effectively, efficiently and harmoniously in the society in which they live. The school should reflect the occupations and lifestyles of the society. Students should be oriented to the needs and challenges of the future society

Saiyidain's Concept of "People's School"

K.G. Saiyidain, a renowned writer on education has opined that school should adequately belong to the people for whom it is intended. He observes "A people's school must obviously be based on the people's needs and problems. Its curriculum should be an epitome of their life. Its method of work must be approximate to theirs. It should reflect all that is significant and characteristic in his life of the community in his natural setting".

According to Saiyidain the school is an epitome of the society. And as such it should introduce all kinds of useful activities and significant features of our day to day life. Students should be given appropriate learning experiences inside the school which they will face in the outside world afterwards. In short, they will be properly trained in the school to assume rightful places in the society in future life.

Community School

A community sets up a school for its child's education. It should provide all facilities in the school and should utilize them for any public purpose, whenever there is need for the same. The Indian society, that is bound to implement a policy that can serve all sections of the society, its heterogeneous nature and diverse challenge, leads to encounter some basic challenges like enrolment, retention of students, motivating parents to send kids to school. This has ended up with one step solution of assistive welfare approach. Schemes like mid-day meal, distribution of cycles, uniforms etc take a centre stage and quality education take a back seat. Adults have an economic approach to the system. The community aspires to utilize the physical resources of the school for its benefit - for adult education, for holding meetings and for organizing community programmes. The minority institutions have a different approach to its outcome but they are constituent of the mainstream education system, as a dichotomous relation? These are called community schools in India that have different functioning as those found in the Philippines, Denmark, England and USA.

The Secondary Education Commission

It is the business of the school to train individuals who will not only be duly appreciative of their culture and the good national character and national traditions but will also be able to analyse and educate it critically to eschew whatever is reactionary and to develop the qualities of high sense of their duty. Only then they are made to realize that they are engaged in the making of better human beings and a better social order and not merely teaching a dull prescribed syllabus. Emphasizing the importance of linking the school life with the life of community, the Commission says, "The starting point of educational reform must be the linking of the school to life and restoring of the intimate relationship between them which has broken down with the development of the formal tradition of education,"

The Commission stresses the importance of close relationship between school and community in these words: "The school will, no doubt, be a community but it will be a small community within a large community and its success and vitality will depend on the constant interplay of healthy influences between it and the large community. What we would like to see is a two-way traffic so that the problems that arise in the home and community life and the realistic outside experiences gained should be brought into school so that education may be based on them and be intimately connected with that life and the in the process the new knowledge, skills, and with real values acquired in the school should be carried into the home life to solve its problems to raise its standards and link up the teachers, community and children in one compact and naturally helpful group.

The above views emphasize the influence of school on society and vice-versa. In this process the child should participate effectively in the societal activities to understand his role in social life, and involve himself in social service. By living within the society the child understands his own duties and responsibilities. He learns his duties and rights. In short the school should develop civic sense, service attitude and co-operative sensibility among children by organising community centred activities in the school.

Economic Influence

Community economy will be influencing the business, trade and other commercial activities of the individuals. The child will be keenly observing specifically the economic activities of individual as well as community in general, Naturally, he will be attracted towards the trades, commercial and professional activities and develops a opinion about his future. This is seen particularly in rural areas. One of the most important functions of school is therefore to maintain continuity of their aspiration vocational skills by providing them relevant opportunities in the schools and also re-organise and reconstruct their vocational skills and aspiration for the promotion of better socio-economic order. In this connection it is apt to quote the opinion of D.S.O Connon "If each generation had to learn for itself what has been learned by its predecessors, no sort of economic, intellectual and social development would be possible and the present state of the society would be little different from the society of the old stone age".

Cultural Influence

Community is a social group living in a particular area and sharing a common cultural heritage. Community transmits its rich cultural heritage to the rising generations. It also trains children in manner that culture and preserve it with indispensable. They inherit tiringly the present day complex set The purpose of school in this regard is to hand down traditions, values, and customs of the society and cultural values, from one generation to the other but also try to enrich and modify the values through their own efforts and then help in the establishment of a better and happier society. Along with socio-economic and democratic ideals, schools should plan to develop the cultural values among children so as to enable them to distinguish between right and wrong and vices. School education must develop among children a sense of appreciation of their culture and civilization.

Community's Role in Education

According to K.G. Sayidain, "Community co-operation is really something more basic for the development of the school. The objectives and purposes of the school, its methods of teaching, the shape of its curriculum, the techniques of teaching and discipline are all ultimately derived from the community in which it functions. If there is no living, dynamic relationship between the two, education will be anemic unreal, unable to make any abiding impact on the mind and character of children. As social purposes change, as the techniques of production develop, as knowledge advances, as the meaning of culture deepens, the life of community is powerfully influenced by all these factors. If the school is not able to keep pace with these changes and adjust its programmes to them, it becomes an outdated, backward- looking agency, an institution only interested in the teaching of certain prescribed course and textbooks which may no longer matter in any significant sense for the contemporary world."

Conclusion

In the light of the above views expressed, the role of community in education is manifold. It includes: Community should aim at providing 'Education for All' by meeting the expenditure as far as possible. Mobilise individual support for compulsory elementary education for children in the age group of 6-14. Interact with the school authorities in various ways particularly in planning institutional plan, curriculum development and school improvement programmes. Encourage teachers participation and students participation in social service activities. Mobilise resources required namely material resources, human resources and financial resources for developing schools.

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